

Quantum Mechanics and Center of Mass Considerations?

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In the literature (1), the Schrodinger equation: $\{p_1^2/2m + p_2^2/2m + V(x_1-x_2)\} W(x_1,x_2,t) = i\hbar/dt \text{ partial } W(x_1,x_2,t)$ may be transformed using $P=p_1+p_2$ and $p=(m_1p_2-m_2p_1)/M$ and $x=x_1-x_2$ where $M=m_1+m_2$ ((1)). This leads to a bound Schrodinger equation in x and a “center of mass” equation” in P i.e. $H_{cm} = PP/2M$ which depends on m_1 and m_2 , but not binding energy. .

In a previous note, we argued that a free particle’s classical action A (relativistic or nonrelativistic) may be obtained by setting $v=x/t$ and treating x and t as independent (2). This leads to $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ and $dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E$. One may write eigenvalue equations: $-i\hbar/dx \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and $i\hbar/dt \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$. A solution is $A=-Et+px$ with E, t, p and x independent. $-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant and this form is used in both relativistic and nonrelativistic quantum mechanics (although E and p have different values).

We argue that a free particle rest mass m_0 may actually involve internal quantum physics, yet the “system” is replaced with a parameter m_0 and $\exp(-iEt+px)$ used to describe it. One may try to apply this approach to a bound system, but $\exp(-iEt+px)$ is a statistical probability like object. Thus one needs a statistical theory. We have suggested using an ensemble of $\exp(-iEt+px)$ with $E=E_n$ for all p to indicate a resonance. Then:

$$\{ \sum \text{over } p \ p^2/2m \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \} / \{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2))$$

This is the Schrodinger bound equation.

We argue that $W = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ should be real and this implies that $\sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) = 0$ i.e. average momentum for this type of average is 0. As a result, one may create a 4-vector using $\{ 0, m_0c + E_n \}$ and use the Lorentz boost approach to find the momentum and energy in a moving frame. One may then take the nonrelativistic limit to find kinetic energy i.e. the full center of mass kinetic energy. We argue that this is equivalent to considering $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ for the overall bound system which is now translating in space.

We argue that ((2)) is a different approach to ((1)) in that binding energy, which may be significant with respect to m_0c^2 , should be part of the overall energy of the translating bound system which is called the “center of mass” system in the literature.

Transformation to Center-of-Mass Coordinates in Quantum Mechanics

In ((1)) and other places in the literature, the quantum Schrodinger equation sometimes is transformed to remove center-of-mass motion from bound motion. For example, in (1) one has:

$$\{p_1^2/2m + p_2^2/2m + V(x_1-x_2)\} W(x_1,x_2,t) = i\hbar/dt \text{ partial } W(x,t) \quad ((3))$$

Using $P=p_1+p_2$ and $p=(m_1p_2-m_2p_1)/M$ where $M=m_1+m_2$ and $u= m_1m_2/(m_1+m_2)$ yields:

$$\{ PP/2M + p^2/2u + V(x) \} W(R_{cm})W_b(x) = (E_{cm}+E_{bound})W(R_{cm})W_b(x) \quad ((4))$$

This approach adds energies i.e E_{cm} and E_{bound} , but E_{cm} only includes m_1 and m_2 and not E_{bound} if one considers $W(R_{cm})$ to represent $\exp(iKR_{cm})$ where K is not 0. If $K=0$, one simply has a bound state which means the system is in a special frame. One may argue that there is no need to have a preferential frame, but we argue that E_n is part of the overall mass energy i.e. $\text{Mass of system} = m_1c^2 + m_2c^2 + E_n$. Given that m_1 and m_2 are used in ((4)), there should be calculation in a so-called rest frame for these. Such a calculation may also be quantum mechanical. If m_1 and m_2 appear as parameters in M and u which are part of kinetic energy of the center of mass, then E_n which is also like mass and may be significant in value should also be part of kinetic energy. Furthermore one may use a rest frame calculation to find E_n and then use a Lorentz boost on $\{0, m_1c^2+m_2c^2+E_n\}$.

Quantum Free Particle Probability and Action

In (2) we note that one may write the free particle relativistic or nonrelativistic classical actions: $A = -m_0 \int \sqrt{1-vv} \quad (c=1)$ and $A = \int .5 m_0 vv$ in terms of $v=x/t$ and vary these independently to find:

$$d/dx \text{ partial } A = p \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dt \text{ partial } A = -E \quad ((4b))$$

Thus operators are used to determine p and E . Writing eigenvalue equations yields:

$$-id/dx \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA) \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad id/dt \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA) \quad ((5b))$$

A solution (relativistic and nonrelativistic) is $A = -Et + px$. This is in the form of a Lorentz invariant, although one should use relativistic values for E and p in such a case. For the nonrelativistic case one uses $E = p^2/2m$ and $p = mv$ where $m = m_0 = \text{rest mass}$.

We argue that a free quantum particle (and a classical one) are closely linked to special relativity. In fact, one may derive the form of special relativity i.e. $m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ etc from this approach. A free particle (or a free system) seems to be linked to the special relativistic form $-Et + px$. No details of m_0 are given even though it may involve subparts of the particle iterating in a quantum manner. For the particle or system, one has a free object given by $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. This same approach should then apply to a quantum bound system. If one is able to create a statistical bound system using $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and it is linked to an energy E_n with average momentum being 0, then the total energy should be:

$$E_{total} = m_1c^2 + m_2c^2 + E_n \quad ((6))$$

One may create a free system represented by $(p=0, E_{total})$ and Lorentz boost. Then one may take nonrelativistic limits. This seems to be a different approach from changing variables and associating one variable with center-of-mass motion which includes nonrelativistically m_1 and m_2 associated with $.5vv$, but not E_n .

Quantum Bound System

One may consider the free particle $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which is a kind of resonance existing in all of space and time with E, t, p and x independent. In classical mechanics $V(x)$ causes local acceleration which is completely at odds with the form $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ unless one has an ensemble of these which somehow add/subtract i.e. interfere to create a v_{rms} which behaves in a classical manner. For equilibrium, one requires an overall constant describing the system which in this case is E_n . All members of the momentum distribution $\sum \over p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ are associated with the same resonance E_n . As a result consider:

$$\left\{ \sum \over p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum \over p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((7))$$

The first term must be real. If $a(p)=a(-p)$ (as an example) then $W(x) = \left\{ \sum \over p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\}$ is real. (In fact, any bound state W is real.) This implies:

$$\sum \over p p \exp(ipx) a(p) = 0 \text{ if } W(x) \text{ drops to zero quickly.} \quad ((8))$$

In other words, one has a system with average momentum ((8)) of 0 and an overall energy E_n . Interestingly, $W(x)$ may span all x , but is usually peaked in a localized region. Given $p_{ave}=0$ and E_n one may create the 4-vector $(0, m_{cc}+E_n)$ and use a Lorentz boost to view it in a moving frame. One may then take the nonrelativistic limit to find the energy and momentum. Expanding the energy in terms of v/v one may find the nonrelativistic kinetic energy i.e. the so-called center of mass kinetic energy.

The fact that one variable x is used in ((7)) is not really an issue because it applies to $x=x_1-x_2$ with $m_1 \gg m_2$. The general idea is that one choose a special nonrelativistic frame to calculate E_n i.e. part of the "rest mass" of the system $m_1 c^2 + m_2 c^2 + E_n$.

In such a case, one would not consider $P^2/2M$ in ((4)) as representing a physically important quantity. One may take the choice that $P=0$.

In other words, one may argue that one creates the Schrodinger equation in this scenario specifically to find a rest mass portion i.e. E_n .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the relativistic or nonrelativistic classical action $A = -Et + px$ is a Lorentz invariant which includes rest mass m_0 as a parameter. We suggest that both relativistic and nonrelativistic quantum mechanics are closely linked to special relativity. One may create eigenvalue equations representing an usual complex probability from the free particle action, namely: $-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ and $i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$. These represent resonances over all space and time with p, E, x and t being independent. If a potential $V(x)$ is present, there is a problem as one cannot have local acceleration if x is independent of t . Rather

one considers an ensemble Sum over p $a(p)\exp(ipx) \exp(-iE_n t)$ with E_n a common resonance energy. This may then be used to calculate average kinetic energy $\{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) p^2 / 2m \ a(p)\exp(ipx)\} / W(x)$ which is equal to $KE(x)$ classical.

As a result, $KE(x)+V(x) = E_n$ where $KE(x) = -1/2m \ d^2/dx^2 W / W$ so only a discrete set of E_n appear. E_n is a binding energy or portion of rest mass. $W(x)$ is real which implies $\text{Integral } dx \ -i d/dx W / W = 0$ so this bound statistical system is equivalent to an average momentum vector 0 and a total energy $m_1 c^2 + m_2 c^2 + E_n$.

For $V(x_1-x_2)$ one has $m_1 c^2 + m_2 c^2 + E_n$ and uses $x = x_1 - x_2$. One deliberately chooses a rest frame to calculate a portion of rest mass namely E_n . Once one knows this (and it may be an appreciable value compared to m_1 and m_2), one may describe the whole bound system as a quantum free particle described by $\exp(-iE_n t + ipx)$. One may use a Lorentz boost to convert $(0, m_1 c^2 + m_2 c^2 + E_n)$ to values seen in a moving frame and then find nonrelativistic limits. We suggest this approach rather than writing $p_1^2 / 2m_1 + p_2^2 / 2m_2 + V(x_1-x_2) = E_n$ ((A)) in terms of a "center-of-mass" piece which only depends on m_1 and m_2 , but not on E_n . If E_n is appreciable, it is not clear what $(p_1+p_2)^2 / 2M$ represents physically for a bound system because it only contains m_1 and m_2 . Even though ((A)) may be separated, one may set E_{cm} in $PP/2M W = E_{cm} W$ to zero as one calculates E_n i.e. a portion of rest mass.

References

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